

Synthetic Investigations on Steroids*

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Stereospecific Synthesis of Equilenin : Bachmann, Cole, and Wilds achieved the first synthesis¹ of equilenin, in which reduction of the unsaturated tricyclic diacid (1) led to simultaneous formation of two isomeric saturated diacids, (2) and (3), which were converted into *d*- and *l*-forms of equilenin and isoequilenin.

The second synthesis² was reported by Johnson, Petersen, and Gutsche, involving a brilliant one step development of the *D*-ring through Stobbe condensation of the tricyclic β -keto nitrile (4) with dimethyl succinate. The resulting tetracyclic unsaturated keto ester (5) on saponification followed by decarboxylation with a boiling mixture of pyridine hydrochloride and hydrochloric acid gave a mixture of tetracyclic unsaturated ketones, (6) and (7), in which the former predominated. The impure unsaturated ketone (7) contaminated with (6), following the separation of pure (6), on repeated treatment with the boiling acid mixture afforded further quantities of pure (6), so that finally a total yield of 66% of the β , γ -unsaturated ketone (6) was realized. Hydrogenation of the α , β -unsaturated ketone (7) gave only *dl*-isoequilenin methyl ether (9), but hydrogenation of (6) yielded a mixture of *dl*-equilenin methyl ether (8) (63%) and (9) (32%).

The third synthesis³ by Johnson and Stromberg constitutes the preparation of the unsaturated ketone (6) by a different method.

* Prof. K. Venkataraman Endowment Lecture (1968).

1. W. E. Bachmann, W. Cole, and A. L. Wilds, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 974; 1940, **62**, 824.
2. W. S. Johnson, J. W. Petersen, and C. D. Gutsche, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2274; 1947, **69**, 2942.
3. W. S. Johnson and V. L. Stromberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 505.

treated with sodium borohydride to obtain the 17β -hydroxy ester (12) in excellent yield; the β -configuration was assigned on the basis of analogy⁷. Saponification of (12) gave exclusively the unsaturated hydroxy acid (13) in contrast with the unsaturated keto acid (14) obtained by Johnson by saponification of (5), the influence of the 17-keto group being manifest in the latter case. Decarboxylation of (13) gave the unsaturated alcohol (15) which was

hydrogenated to give exclusively the saturated alcohol (16). Oxidation of (16) gave *dl*-equilenin methyl ether. Thus, the first stereospecific synthesis⁸ of equilenin was achieved. Later⁹, for large scale preparation of *dl*-equilenin methyl ether (8), it was found more expedient to prepare the unsaturated ketone (6) by the method of Johnson² followed by treatment of (6) with sodium borohydride to get the unsaturated alcohol (15), as decarboxylation of large quantities of the unsaturated hydroxy acid (13) at a time proved difficult.

7. L. F. Fieser, *Experientia*, 1950, **6**, 312; C. W. Shoppee, *Nature*, 1950, **166**, 107.

8. D. K. Banerjee, S. Chatterjee, C. N. Pillai and M. V. Bhatt, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 3769.

9. D. K. Banerjee, B. Sugavanam and G. Nadamuni, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1969, **69**, 233, 243.

In the endeavour to develop a benzohydrindane approach to the total synthesis of steroids, an entirely new stereospecific synthesis of the equilenin molecule was reported¹⁰ by Banerjee and Johnson and coworkers. β -(6-Methoxy-1-naphthyl)-propionic acid (17), prepared from β -(6-methoxy-1-naphthyl)-ethyl bromide by treatment with potassium cyanide followed by saponification, was converted through its acid chloride to β -(6-Methoxy-1-naphthyl)-ethyl methyl ketone (18). Condensation of (18) with ethyl cyanoacetate followed by the addition of hydrogen cyanide and cyanoethylation gave the tricyano ester (19). Hydrolysis and decarboxylation of (19) and subsequent esterification furnished the triester (20). The β -keto ester (21) obtained by Dieckmann cyclization of (20) on treatment with hydrogen fluoride afforded the unsaturated tetracyclic diester (22a). The corresponding diacid (22b) was decarboxylated to give the mono acid (23), and the latter on hydrogenation gave 3-methoxy-17-carboxyequilbenane (24) as a single product. The structure and the *trans* C/D-fusion were proved by its identity with the acid prepared from *dl*-equilenin methyl ether *via* the cyanohydrin (25), the unsaturated cyano compound (26), and the hydrogenated product (27).

10. D. K. Banerjee, H. N. Khastgir, J. Dutta, and E. J. Jacob and W. S. Johnson, C. F. Allen, B. K. Bhattacharyya, J. C. Collins (Jr.), A. L. McCloskey, W. T. Tsatsos, W. A. Vredenburg and K. L. Williamson, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1961, 76.

A third stereospecific synthesis of the equilenin molecule has been very recently reported¹¹. This involved utilization of ethyl 2-methyl-3-carbethoxycyclopentanone-2-acetate (34b) as the starting material. This keto diester with the proved structure and steric configuration was prepared by Banerjee and Das Gupta¹² from ethyl α -acetylglutarate (28) by the method outlined below. Condensation of (28) with ethyl cyanoacetate gave the unsaturated cyano ester (29) along with the by-product (30)¹³. The dicyano ester (31) obtained by the addition of hydrogen cyanide to (30) on hydrolysis followed by esterification furnished the tetraester (32). Dieckmann cyclization of (32) gave the β -keto ester (33) which

was hydrolysed, decarboxylated, and esterified to yield the keto diester (34b). The *trans*-configuration of (34) was proved by converting the diacid (34a) to the *cis*-diacid (36) via the anhydride (35). The structure of (34b) was proved by converting it to a mixture of already known¹⁴ *cis*- and *trans*-1-methyl-2-carboxycyclopentaneacetic acids (37). Authentic samples

11. D. K. Banerjee, M. Mahishi, and D. Devaprabhakara, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 479.

12. D. K. Banerjee and S. K. Das Gupta, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1318.

13. D. K. Banerjee, P. S. Gupta and S. K. Das Gupta, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, 19, 1516.

14. C. Chung, C. Ma, and S. Tien, *Ber.*, 1935, 68, 1946; cf. K. D. Errington and R. P. Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 6

of these isomeric acids (37) were prepared by an independent method¹² from ethyl 2-methylcyclopentanone-2-acetate (38), earlier prepared by Chakravarty and Banerjee¹⁵, by converting it to the unsaturated nitrile ester (39), *via* the cyanohydrin, followed by hydrolysis and hydrogenation.

Condensation of 2-methoxy-6-lithionaphthalene (40) with the keto diester (34b), following the procedure of Newman *et al.*¹⁶, and treatment of the resulting crude product with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid in benzene followed by saponification afforded the unsaturated diacid (41a). Cyclization of (41a) and the corresponding dimethyl ester (41b) with PPA gave the tetracyclic unsaturated keto acid (42a) and the ester (42b) respectively. Catalytic hydrogenation of (42a) furnished the saturated keto acid (43) after absorption of one mole of hydrogen, whereas, allowing the hydrogenation to proceed to the end, when it absorbed two more moles of hydrogen, the tetracyclic carboxylic acid (24), identical in all respects with the acid previously prepared by Banerjee and Johnson and coworkers, was obtained.

Stereospecific synthesis of oestrone: The preparation of a model keto diester (49) was reported¹⁷ in 1947 by Banerjee and Dutta by the route outlined below with the aim to develop a new method for the synthesis of oestrone. Condensation of ethyl γ -benzoylbutyrate (44) with ethyl cyanoacetate gave the unsaturated cyano ester (45) which was reduced with aluminium amalgam in moist ether to afford diethyl α -cyano- β -phenylpimelate (46). The sodio derivative of (46) was interacted with ethyl bromoacetate to furnish the cyano triester (47) which on hydrolysis and esterification yielded the triester (48). Dieckmann cyclization of (48) followed by methylation furnished the keto diester (49).

Later, Turner¹⁸ shortened the number of steps by employing Stobbe condensation and obtained the product (49) in the pure crystalline form.

15. N. K. Chakravarty and D. K. Banerjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, **24**, 377.

16. G. Eglinton, J. C. Nevenzel, A. I. Scott, and M. S. Newman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 2331.

17. J. Dutta and D. K. Banerjee, *Science and Culture*, 1947, **12**

18. D. L. Turner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 3017.

The methoxy derivative (51, R = OCH₃) in the correct steric form, along with another isomer, was synthesized by both Turner¹⁹ and Johnson *et al.*²⁰ using methyl γ -anisoylbutyrate (50, R = OCH₃) as the starting material; the ethyl γ -anisoylbutyrate²¹ was prepared for the first time in our laboratory. An ingenious method for the preparation of the keto diester

(51, R = OCH₃), also as a stereoisomeric mixture, was later developed⁴ by Bhattacharyya and Sen Gupta²². Protiva *et al.*²³ repeated the experiments of Bhattacharyya and were successful in obtaining the pure desired isomer (51, R = OCH₃), as the major product, by careful chromatography.

19. D. L. Turner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1284.
20. W. S. Johnson and R. G. Christiansen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5511; W. S. Johnson, R. G. Christiansen, and R. E. Ireland, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 1995.
21. D. K. Banerjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 573.
22. B. K. Bhattacharyya and P. Sengupta, *Nature*, 1952, **170**, 710; *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 337.
23. J. O. Jilek, V. Simak and M. Protiva, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, **47**, 874; *Collection Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1954, **19**, 333; *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, **49**, 197.

It was Johnson and coworkers²⁰ who ultimately achieved the stereoselective conversion of the keto diester (51, R = OCH₃) to *dl*-oestrone methyl ether (52), as shown below.

Considering that a stereospecific synthesis of the keto diester (51, R = OCH₃) would render this route entirely stereospecific and might constitute a practicable method for the preparation of oestrone, we developed the following procedure²⁴ to achieve this objective.

Condensation of β -dimethylamino-*p*-methoxypropiofenone hydrochloride (53) with diethyl β -oxo-adipate (54)²⁵ in presence of sodium ethoxide followed by treatment with

24. D. K. Banerjee and K. Sivanandaiah, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, 20; *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 652.

25. D. K. Banerjee and K. M. Sivanandaiah, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1634.

dimethyl sulphate gave the product (55) which, by refluxing with 10% alkali, was converted into the unsaturated keto acid (56, R = H) in 90% yield. The compound (56) on reduction with lithium and anhydrous ammonia²⁶ gave the *trans*-saturated keto acid (57, R = H) in 80% yield. The methyl ester (57, R = CH₃) was stereospecifically converted, *via* the isoxazole (58, 63%) and the methylated keto cyano ester (59, 75%), to the keto diester (51, R = OCH₃, 72%). The keto cyano ester (59) was also prepared by Johnson²⁷ by a different route. Another stereospecific route, which gave a lower yield, consisted in the conversion of unsaturated keto ester (56, R = CH₃), *via* the isoxazole (60, 36%) and the unsaturated cyano keto acid (61, 63%), to the keto diester (51, R = OCH₃, 34%).

Stereospecific synthesis of trans-benzohydrindane derivatives: It was realized quite early that suitably substituted *trans* benzohydrindane derivatives might serve as valuable intermediates for the total synthesis of steroids and their analogues, and it has been possible to develop two distinct methods^{8,10} for the stereospecific syntheses of five such derivatives.

Stereospecific synthesis of trans-1 β -hydroxy-8-methyl-4,5-(4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane and trans-1 β -hydroxy-8-methyl-4,5(3'-methyl-4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane: For the preparation of two of these derivatives, *viz.*, *trans*-1 β -hydroxy-8-methyl-4,5-(4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane (65a) and *trans*-1 β -hydroxy-8-methyl-4,5-(3'-methyl-4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane (65b), initially 6-methoxytetralone (62a) and 5-methyl-6-methoxytetralone (62b) were converted into methyl 1-keto-8-methyl-4,5-(4'-methoxybenzo) $\Delta^{3(9)}$ -hydrindene-3-carboxylate (63a) and methyl 1-keto-8-methyl-4,5-(3'-methyl-4'-methoxybenzo)- $\Delta^{3(9)}$ -hydrindene-3-carboxylate (63b) respectively by following the procedure of Johnson, and later the compounds, (63a) and (63b), were converted stereospecifically into (65a) and (65b) respectively by following the method of Banerjee. The scheme is outlined below.

In this connection it may be mentioned that two isomers of each of the ketones corresponding to the hydroxy compounds, (65a) and (65b), were earlier prepared by Bachmann

26. D. K. Banerjee, S. Chatterjee, and S. P. Bhattacharyya, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 408.

27. W. S. Johnson, R. E. Ireland, and R. E. Tarney, "Steroids", Fieser and Fieser, p. 500, Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1959.

and Thomas²⁸ and Martin and Robinson²⁹ respectively by following the procedure of Bachmann, Cole and Wilds for the synthesis of equilenin. While the former workers did not assign configurations to their isomeric ketones, Robinson indicated probable configurations on the basis of solubility. Our investigations^{8,30} permitted definite configurations to be assigned to all four isomers, and Robinson's assignment was found to be correct.

Stereospecific synthesis of trans-1 β -carboxy-8-methyl-4,5-(4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane, trans-1 β -carboxy-4,5-(3'-methyl-4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane, and trans-1 β ,6-dicarboxy-4,5-(4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane: The starting materials, 3-methoxybenzylacetone (66, R = R' = H), 2-methyl-3-methoxybenzylacetone (66, R = CH₃, R' = H), and 3-methoxy-(α -cyano- γ -ketobutyl)-benzene (66, R = H; R' = CN), were first converted in excellent yields to the triesters, (67, R = R' = H), (67, R = CH₃, R' = H) and (67, R = H, R' = COOCH₃), respectively by the following reaction sequence: condensation with ethyl cyanoacetate, addition of hydrogen cyanide, cyano-ethylation, hydrolysis, and esterification. Dieckmann cyclization gave the keto diesters, (68, R = R' = H), (68, R = CH₃, R' = H) and (68, R = H, R' = COOCH₃), respectively, which on acid-catalyzed ring closure, followed by hydrolysis and decarboxylation, afforded the acids, (69, R = R' = H), (69, R = CH₃, R' = H) and (69, R = H, R' = CO₂H), respectively. Catalytic hydrogenation of these acids proceeded stereoselectively to give *trans*-1 β -carboxy-8-methyl-4,5-(4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane (70, R = R' = H), *trans*-1 β -carboxy-8-methyl-4,5-(3'-methyl-4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane (70, R = CH₃, R' = H), and *trans*-1 β ,6-dicarboxy-4,5-(4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane (70, R = H, R' = COOH) respectively.

28. W. E. Bachmann and D. G. Thomas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 94.

29. R. H. Martin and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 491.

30. D. K. Banerjee and S. K. Balasubramanian, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 105.

The best method of preparing (70, R = CH₃, R' = H), however, involved condensation of (66, R = CH₃, R' = H) with *t*-butyl cyanoacetate, addition of hydrogen cyanide, and cyanoethylation to give a mixture of diastereoisomers. Pyrolysis removed the *carbo-t*-butoxyl group to give the trinitrile corresponding to (67, R = CH₃, R' = H) which on *t*-butoxide-catalyzed Thorpe cyclization yielded two isomeric forms of (71). The mixture of isomers was hydrolysed and then cyclized with hydrogen fluoride to obtain two isomers, the mixture of which on alkaline hydrolysis, decarboxylation, and hydrogenation furnished (70, R = CH₃, R' = H) in 41% yield from the ketone (66, R = CH₃, R' = H).

Total synthesis of 8-isotestosterone and the analogous anthratestosterone: Djerassi *et al*³¹. reported a multi-stage conversion of diosgenin to 8-isotestosterone which, besides retaining nearly one half the biological activity of testosterone, presents an interesting conformational feature in that the B ring exists in the boat form³². The latter factor made the total synthesis of this molecule particularly attractive, and the conversion of the benzohydrindane derivative (65, R = CH₃) to *dl*-8-isotestosterone was achieved by the method described below³³.

The compound (65, R = CH₃) was demethylated to the hydroxy phenol (72). The use of pyridinium chloride instead of methyl magnesium iodide greatly simplified this operation, while the yield was only reduced from 79% to 75%. The preferential acetylation of (72) to give the phenol acetate (73) in 70% yield was achieved by refluxing (72) in acetic acid in the presence of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid following the procedure of Chen³⁴, the ester exchange procedure with ethyl acetate and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid as well as the selective saponification of the diacetate of (72) giving lower yields. Catalytic hydrogenation of (73) using 5% ruthenium on carbon catalyst at 300 atmospheres pressure and 100° afforded mainly (74) besides small quantities of the hydrogenolyzed material (75) and a gummy product. The major product was assigned the configuration (74) because catalytic hydrogenation of (73) was expected to take place from the less hindered α -side of the molecule since the bulky methyl group would, following Linstead's⁴ concept, offer serious hindrance to the approach of the molecule on the catalyst surface from the same side. Oxidation of (74) with Jones' reagent gave the keto acetate (76). Similar oxidation of the gummy fraction (which proceeded at a slower rate) afforded more of (76) and, in addition, an isomeric material which has been assigned the configuration (77). These results and the fact that the gummy fraction of the product of hydrogenation was eluted from the column immediately after the product (74) led us to assume that during the catalytic hydrogenation of (73), its adsorption on the catalyst surface to a small extent from the same side as the angular methyl group resulted also in the formation of the isomeric hydroxy acetate (78). The mode of hydrogenation indicated axial and equatorial hydroxyls for (74) and (78) respectively. Further, their behaviour during chromatography as well as in chromic acid oxidation supported these

31. C. Djerassi, A. J. Manson and H. Bendas, *Tetrahedron*, 1957, **1**, 22.
32. C. Djerassi, R. Riniker, and B. Riniker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 6362, 6377.
33. D. K. Banerjee, V. Paul, and S. K. Balasubramanian, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, **23**; D. K. Banerjee, V. Paul, S. K. Balasubramanian, and P. S. N. Murthy, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 2487.
34. C. Chen, private communication; cf. *Tetrahedron*, 1958, **3**, 43.
35. A. J. Birch and H. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4909.

assignments. If it were assumed that part of the axial hydroxyl of (74) had epimerized during hydrogenation or chromatography, then the new isomer (79) and (78) might be expected to elute at about the same rate to give a mixture. This assumption has been confirmed later by isolation³⁶ of the isomer (79) in the pure state by more careful chromatography and oxidizing it to the keto acetate (76). Recovery of the keto acetate (76), unaffected after treatment with potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol, indicating an equatorial conformation of the methyl group adjacent to the carbonyl in (76), further confirmed our views.

Axial alkylation at the methine carbon in (76), expected to be aided by hyperconjugation, should take place from the convex face of the *cis*-2-decalone cage and the resulting product could cyclize only by forcing the B-ring into a boat conformation. Addition of methyl vinyl ketone to (76) in presence of Triton B furnished a crystalline α, β -unsaturated ketone, identified as *dl*-8-isotestosterone (80) by comparing its IR spectrum with the IR spectrum (kindly furnished by Professor Djerassi) of *d*-8-isotestosterone. Additional proof in favour of the structure (80) was provided by condensation of the methylanilinomethylene derivative of (76) with methyl vinyl ketone followed by removal of the blocking group to afford a material, same as that obtained by direct alkylation.

Condensation of the hydroxymethylene derivatives of the keto acetate (76) with vinyl methyl ketone followed by removal of the formyl group gave an α, β -unsaturated ketone, different from (80), and this compound has been assigned the anthraterestosterone structure (81).

Syntheses of 8-iso-19-noranthraterestosterone and 8-iso-10-iso-19-nortestosterone : In continuation of the syntheses³³ of *dl*-8-iso-testosterone (80) and 8-iso-anthraterestosterone (81), the investigation on the synthesis of the corresponding 19-nor analogues was undertaken. This led to the syntheses^{9,37} of 8-iso-19-noranthraterestosterone (93) and 8-iso-10-iso-19-nortestosterone

36. D. K. Banerjee and P. S. N. Murthy, unpublished work.

37. D. K. Banerjee, B. Sugavanam, and G. Nadamuni, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 2771.

(97). The obvious starting material for the former (93) was the benzohydrindane derivative (65a). Demethylation of *dl*-(65a) with pyridinium chloride afforded the hydroxy phenol (82) in 80% yield. In contrast to our previous observation with the higher homologue (72), the acetoxy phenol (84) was obtained in an overall yield of 86% from (82) by selective saponification of the diacetate (83). Catalytic hydrogenation of (84) with either Raney nickel (W_2) or ruthenium on carbon 5% furnished the hydroxy acetate (85) as the major product, a very small quantity of its isomer (86) together with the diol (87), and a gum. Oxidation of the isomeric hydroxy acetates, (85) and (86), with Jones' reagent yielded the identical keto acetate (89, R = Ac). A small quantity of (89, R = Ac) was also obtained by oxidation of the gum. Saponification of the hydroxy acetate (85) gave a diol (88), different from the diol (87) described earlier, but both on oxidation produced the identical diketone (90), presumably the axial C-6 hydroxyl of (85) epimerized during saponification.

Because of considerable accumulation of the diol (87) from several hydrogenation experiments, it was converted to the hydroxy ketone (89, R = H), *via* the diketone (90) and its monoketal (91), by treatment of the latter with sodium borohydride and removal of the ethylenedioxy group.

To determine the position of the hydroxymethylene group, 5 or 7, in the product obtained by condensation of the keto acetate (89, R = Ac) with ethyl formate, the crude hydroxymethylene derivative was methylated and treated with alcoholic hydrochloric acid. The resulting gummy product, on acetylation, furnished a methylated keto acetate, in which the methyl group should be equatorial because of the equilibrating condition of the cleavage of the formyl group. This compound was found to be different from the keto acetate (76) in which the methyl group was proved³³ to be equatorial by the equilibration experiment. Therefore the methylated keto acetate should be represented by (92) and the hydroxymethylene group attached to the 7-position. The crude hydroxymethylene derivative on condensation with methyl vinyl ketone afforded *dl*-8-iso-19-noranthraterostosterone (93) and a minute quantity of another crystalline material, presumably the β , γ -isomer (94).

At this stage, Velluz *et al.* in a short communication³⁸ disclosed the total synthesis of *d*-8-iso-19-nortestosterone (95)³⁹ and its ethylenic isomer (96) by direct condensation of methyl vinyl ketone with the *d*-keto acetate (89, R = Ac), the latter being prepared from *d*-(65a) following identical steps described by us³³ for the synthesis of *dl*-8-isotestosterone (80). Later, in a more detailed account they claimed^{40a} the preparation of *d*- and *l*-(95), *d*- and *l*-8-iso-10-iso-19-nortestosterone (97), and the *d*- and *l*- β , γ -isomer (96).

These results prompted us to prepare (96) and (97) by the following unambiguous method. *dl*-Dihydroequilenin (98) was hydrogenated with Raney nickel (W_5) in an alkaline medium to furnish *dl*-8-isoestradiol (99, R = H) in 21% yield, along with a neutral material. Birch reduction of the methyl ether (99, R = CH_3) followed by hydrolysis with oxalic acid furnished *dl*-8-iso-17 β -hydroxy-19-norandrost-5(10)-en-3-one (96). Treatment of (96) with methanolic hydrochloric acid gave a mixture of β , γ - (major product), and σ , β -unsaturated keto alcohols, which were separated by "Inverted Dry Column Chromatography".⁴¹ The IR spectrum ($CHCl_3$) of the β , γ -isomer (96) was identical with the sample obtained

38. L. Velluz, G. Nomine, and R. Bucourt, *C.R.Acad. Sci. Paris*, 1963, **257**, 811.

39. The configuration has since been changed to 8-iso-10-iso-19-nortestosterone, private communication.

40a. R. Bucourt and G. Nomine, *Fr. 1,404, 413* (C 107c); *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, **63**, 18212b; (b) Private communication.

41. Dr. Sukh Dev, private communication; V. K. Bhalla, U. R. Nayak, and Shukh Dev, *J. Chromatog.*, 1967, **26**, 54.

from Dr. Velluz. The IR spectrum (nujol) of the aforementioned α , β -isomer was different from that of the α , β -unsaturated keto alcohol (93). Although Djerassi³² suggested a boat conformation for the B-ring in 8-isotestosterone on the basis of ORD data, yet the possibility of enolization of the C-10 hydrogen of the corresponding 19-nor compound, under the equilibrating condition employed for isomerization of the β , γ -isomer (96), led us to assign α -configuration to it with the preferred all chair arrangement (97). To prove the configuration with the help of ORD data of the authentic optically active 19-nor compound, we catalytically hydrogenated *d*-17, 17-ethylenedioxyestra-1,3,5(10),6,8-pentaen-3-ol (100), prepared by refluxing *d*- ϵ -quilenin with ethylene glycol, ethyl orthoformate, and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, as the synthesis of B-ring aromatic compounds with the 17-keto group intact also formed a part of our programme. The phenolic fraction, obtained after removal of the ethylenedioxy group, consisting of two compounds, proved to be *d*-8-isoestrone (major product) and *d*-9-isoestrone by comparison of their IR spectra with those of authentic samples. *d*-8-Isoestrone was methylated and converted to the optically active, β , γ - and α , β -unsaturated keto alcohols. Mixture melting point determination and the IR spectra (nujol) of Velluz's sample and our authentic *d*-(96) proved their identity. The shapes of the ORD curves (Fig. 1) of *d*- α , β -isomer and *d*-8-isotestosterone were different, proving the α -configuration of the C-10 hydrogen of the former (97). The ORD curve (Fig. 1) of the sample of *d*-8-iso-10-iso 19-nortestosterone, furnished by Dr. Nomine and Dr. Bucourt, was identical with that of our authentic compound (97); the mixture melting point was also not depressed. Torgov *et al.*⁴² claimed the preparation of *dl*-8-iso-19-nortestosterone (95). Later, Smith⁴³

42. K. K. Koshoev, S. N. Ananchenko, and I. V. Torgov, *Khim. Prirodn. Soedin., Akad. Nauk USSR.*, 1965, **3**, 180; *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, **63**, 13346f; cf. V. I. Zaretskii, N. S. Wulfson, and V. L. Sadovskaya, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 3879.
43. G. C. Buzby, (Jr.), E. Capaldi, G. H. Douglas, D. Hartley, D. Herbst, G. A. Hughes, K. Ledig, L. McMenamin, T. Pattison, H. Smith, C. R. Walk, G. R. Wendt, J. Siddal, B. Gadsby, and A. B. A. Jansen, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 338; cf. A. J. Birch and G. S. R. Subba Rao, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 5139.

carried out the same experiment and suggested the possibility of the presence of the 10α -compound (97) in the mixture he obtained. On the basis of the present work, Torgov's compound should be *dl*-8-iso-10-iso-19-nortestosterone (97).

The ORD curve (Fig. 1) with negative Cotton effect of the sample supplied by Dr. Nomine and Dr. Bucourt as 3-oxo-17 β -hydroxy-8 α -oestra-4-ene (95) was entirely different from the positive ORD curve of *d*-8-isotestosterone (80). Therefore 40b compound appears not to be 8-iso-19-nortestosterone (95). But they have proved the structure.

Total synthesis of 3 β -hydroxy-17-ketooestra-5,7,9-triene and its α -isomer: Heard and Hoffman⁴⁴, in 1940, isolated a keto alcohol from pregnant equine urine, to which they assigned the structure and configuration (101). Its conversion to the diol (102) formed the basis for assignment of the β -configuration to the 3-hydroxyl. The diol (102) and its α -epimer (103)

44. R. D. H. Heard and M. M. Hoffman, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1940, **135**, 801; 1941, **138**, 651.

were obtained by Ruzicka *et al.*⁴⁵ from *d*-equilenin by catalytic hydrogenation and by sodium and alcohol reduction respectively, and the configurations at the 3-position were assigned on the assumption that the 3 β -hydroxy compound should have more negative optical rotation and lower melting point than those of the α -epimer. Later, Glen *et al.*⁴⁶ could obtain the same alcohol (101) in larger quantities from the same source. Considerable interest also centres round this B-aromatic steroid (101) because of the recent postulate⁴⁷ which considers the compound (101) as one of the metabolites, along with equilin (106) and equilenin (107) of 3 β -hydroxyandrost-5-en-17-one (108).

Remesow⁴⁸ claimed to have converted neoergosterol to (101) by an oxidative degradation, but its UV spectrum, λ_{max} 282 m μ ϵ 2000, and the high biological activity were entirely different from those of the urinary steroid (101). Harnik⁴⁹ suggested that Remesow's compound might be the 3 α -epimer (104).

The syntheses of the urinary steroid (101) and its 3 α -epimer (104) have now been achieved⁵⁰ starting from equilenin (107) and dihydroequilenin (98, R = H), as described below.

We hydrogenated *dl*-equilenin (107), *dl*-dihydroequilenin (98, R = H), and *d*-equilenin ethylene ketal (100) under the conditions of Dauben⁵¹. *dl*-Equilenin and *dl*-dihydroequilenin furnished two neutral diols along with 8-isoestradiol (99, R = H), the yields in the latter case being better. The two diols, on preferential oxidation, gave different keto alcohols

45. L. Ruzicka and P. Muller, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1938, **21**, 1394; cf. K. David, *Acta brev. Neerl.*, 1938, **8**, 211 and R. E. Marker, E. Rohrmann, E. L. Wittle, and F. H. Tendick, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2441.
46. W. L. Glen, R. Barber, and G. Papineau-Couture, *Nature*, 1958, **182**, 1308.
47. L. Starka and H. Breuer, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta.*, 1966, **115**, 306; *Hoppe-Seylers Z. physiol. chem.*, 1966, **344**, 124; L. Starka, H. Breuer, and L. Cedard, *J. Endocrinol.*, 1966, **34**, 447.
48. I. Remesow, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1936, **55**, 797.
49. M. Harnik, *Israel J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 183.
50. D. K. Banerjee and G. Nadamuni, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 529.
51. W. G. Dauben and L. Ahramjian, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 633.

in which the keto groups were proved to be at C-17 by the position, 45 cps, of the 18-methyl signal in the NMR, the carbonyl absorption at 1738 cm^{-1} in the IR, and finally by showing them to be different from the 3-keto-17 β -alcohol (105), prepared from *dl*-dihydroequilenin methyl ether (98, R = CH₃) following the method of Cornforth⁵², by direct comparison. Both the 17-keto alcohols could be reduced with sodium borohydride to the respective parent diols, showing β -configuration⁷ of the 17-hydroxyl in the two diols. The inversion⁵³ of one of the keto alcohols, *via* its inverted formate, to furnish the other isomeric keto alcohol proved them to be epimers at the position-3.

Normally two mobile half-chair conformations, (109) and (110), of the ring-A would lead one to expect the sodium borohydride reduction of the 3-keto-17 β -alcohol (105) to give two epimeric alcohols in equal proportion, as both can have equatorial conformation. However, Levine *et al.*⁵⁴ observed conformational preference in the case 5(10)-unsaturated 3-keto compounds, where the conformation (109) was found to have severe interaction between 1 β - and 11 α -hydrogens, while the conformation (110) was free from such interaction. Actually, sodium borohydride reduction of (105) furnished mainly the higher melting diol. Following the principle⁵⁵ that an unhindered ketone on reduction with complex hydrides gives mainly the more stable equatorial alcohol, α -configuration has been assigned to the 3-hydroxyl of the higher melting diol (103) and to the corresponding oxidation product, the 3-hydroxy-17-ketone (104). The IR (CHCl₃) spectrum of the acetate of 3-hydroxy-17-ketone (101), the oxidation product of the lower melting diol (102), was found to be identical with the acetate of the urinary steroid, kindly supplied by Dr. Glen.

Hydrogenation of *d*-equilenin ketal (100) furnished two neutral ketals. The one obtained in very small amount did not depress the melting point of the ketal of the urinary steroid on admixture, but the major product did. The keto alcohol, generated from the major ketal, had an IR spectrum (CHCl₃) identical with that of the natural steroid, but the melting points were different. This keto alcohol on reduction with sodium borohydride gave a diol with the melting point corresponding to that of the diol (103) of Ruzicka with the 3 α -hydroxyl.

Synthesis of 10-iso-9(11)-dehydrotestosterone: Lithium-liquid ammonia-ethanol reduction of the benzohydrindane derivative (65b) under specific conditions³⁵ gave the unsaturated keto alcohol (111, R = H) as its 2,4-DNP, the highest yield so far achieved being 34%. The pure (111, R = H) could be obtained by regeneration from its derivative. Hydrogenation

52. J. W. Cornforth, R. H. Cornforth, and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 689.

53. F. C. Cheng and R. T. Blickenstaff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 2907.

54. S. G. Levine, N. H. Endy and E. C. Farthing, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1963, 1517; S. G. Levine, N. H. Endy and C. F. Leffler, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 3995.

55. D. H. R. Barton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1027.

of the unsaturated keto alcohol and its benzoate (111, R = CO.C₆H₅) over 2% Pd-SrCO₃ in ethanol in presence of 25% aqueous potassium hydroxide gave the saturated keto alcohol (112, R = H) and its benzoate (112, R = CO.C₆H₅) respectively.⁵⁶ Optical antipodes of all these compounds, (111, R = H), (111, R = CO.C₆H₅), (112, R = H), and (112, R = CO.C₆H₅), were previously obtained by Hartshorn and Jones⁵⁷ by the degradation of testosterone. The IR spectra of the unsaturated keto alcohol benzoate (111, R = CO.C₆H₅) in chloroform and the saturated keto alcohol benzoate (112, R = CO.C₆H₅) in carbon disulphate were identical with those of degradation products. The identity in the latter case showed that the axial C-10 methyl group, resulting from the addition of hydrogen to (111) from the α -face

of the molecule, had epimerized to the more stable equatorial conformation in presence of alkali.

Condensation of the unsaturated keto alcohol (111, R = H) with methyl vinyl ketone in presence of Triton B afforded 10-iso-9(11)-dehydrotestosterone (113). The configuration of the 10-methyl group was assigned on the basis of the non-identity of the IR spectra of (113) and an authentic specimen of 9(11)-dehydrotestosterone, kindly furnished by Dr. Nomine and Dr. Bucourt.

56. D. K. Banerjee, P. S. N. Murthy and V. Paul, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967, 1879.

57. M. P. Hartshorn and E. R. H. Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1312.

Total synthesis of 3-keto-17 β -carboxyoestra-4-ene: The benzohydrindane derivative (70, R = R' = H) on reduction with lithium and ammonia followed by treatment with warm dilute sulphuric acid gave an excellent yield of 17 β -carboxy-des-A-oestra-9-en-5-one (114). The unsaturated keto acid (114) on further reduction with lithium-ammonia-methanol furnished the hydroxy acid (115), which on esterification and oxidation afforded the keto ester (116). Following the model study⁵⁸ by Banerjee *et al.* for the conversion of *trans*-2-decalone to *trans*-2,3,4,4a,4b,5,6,7,8,8a,9,10-dodecahydro-2-phenanthrone, the keto ester (116) was converted to the 6-methylanilinomethylene derivative (117) and the latter treated with ethyl formate in presence of potassium methoxide and then with methyl vinyl ketone in presence of Triton B. The resulting crude product on refluxing with aqueous alkali gave 17 β -carboxyoestra-4-en-3-one (118)⁵⁹ in 4.5% yield.

The tetracyclic unsaturated keto acid (118) could also be obtained⁶⁰, but again in extremely poor yield, by reductive alkylation⁶¹ of the tricyclic unsaturated keto acid (114) with 1,3-dichlorobutene followed by treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid.

Total synthesis of 3-methoxy-17 β -carbomethoxyestra-1,3,5(10)-triene: The dienamine (120), obtained in excellent yield from the unsaturated keto ester (119) and pyrrolidine, on treatment with methyl vinyl ketone followed by hydrolysis furnished a mixture of the diketo ester (121) and the dienone ester (122). The structure of the former was confirmed by NMR spectrum. The crude dienone ester (122) was treated with methanolic sodium hydroxide and then refluxed with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate to give 3-methoxy-17 β -carbomethoxyestra-1,3,5(10)-triene (123)⁶².

An investigation on the building of ring A of steroids: The development of ring A, following Birch reduction of the benzohydrindane system, has always been difficult, because of steric factors and low yield in the alkylation step. We considered that the benzohydrindane derivative (70, R = H, R' = CO₂H) on Birch reduction followed by esterification might

58. D. K. Banerjee, S. Chatterjee and S. P. Bhattacharya, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 408.

59. D. K. Banerjee, W. S. Johnson, and E. J. Jacob, unpublished work.

60. D. K. Banerjee, W. S. Johnson, and K. Srinivasan, unpublished work.

61. G. Stork, P. Rosen, N. Goldman, R. V. Coombs, and J. Tsuji, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 275.

62. D. K. Banerjee, W. S. Johnson and K. Srinivasan, unpublished work.

furnish the Hagemann ester system (124) distributed in rings B and C, and this could be expected to be easily alkylated at the required position because of its reactivity as a vinylogous β -keto ester. For the preliminary study⁶³ we chose 7-methoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthoic acid (125) as the model compound. Reduction of the acid (125) with lithium-ammonia-ethanol followed by hydrolysis of the enol ether, esterification, and migration of the double bond gave methyl 7-keto-1,2,3,4,4a,5,6,7-octahydronaphthoate (126) with the UV λ_{max} 236 m μ . Alkylation of (126) with ethyl β -chloropropionate in presence of potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol gave the expected 7-keto-8- β -carbethoxyethyl-1,2,3,4,4a,5,6,7-octahydronaphthoate (127). The structure of (127) was proved by degrading it to 1- β -carbo-methoxyethyl- $\Delta^{1(9)}$ -octal-2-one (128) by treatment with aqueous methanolic potassium hydroxide followed by esterification and by direct comparison of its semicarbazone with that of an authentic specimen prepared by the condensation of 2-hydroxymethylcyclohexanone (129) with methyl 5-keto-6-heptenoate (130) in presence of potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol followed by the successive treatment with alkali and diazomethane.

A stereospecific synthesis of trans-1 β -hydroxy-7-methoxy-11-methyl-1,2,3,4,9,10,11,12-octahydrophenanthrene: In a review⁶⁴ on "Recent advances in the total synthesis of steroids", Velluz *et al.* have described the development of the first syntheses suitable for the industrial production of natural steroid hormones. For most of these preparations they have utilized the optically active benzohydrindane derivative (65, a), prepared by our method, as the starting material, optical resolution having been carried out at the stage of the tricyclic hydroxy acid (64a). On the basis of this work it appeared that the corresponding *trans*-benzodecalone derivative (134) would be the ideal starting material for the synthesis of D-homosteroids. Our stereospecific synthesis⁶⁵ of the compound (134) involved preparation of dialkylated dihydro-resorcinol in the first step. Birth and Smith⁶⁶ had already observed that a monoalkylated dihydroresorcinol dimethyl ether could not be further alkylated. But, 2- β -(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-ethylcyclohexan-1,3-dione (131), prepared by the method of

63. D. K. Banerjee, J. Dutta, A. S. Rao, and E. J. Jacob, *Tetrahedron*, 1960, **8**, 163.

64. L. Veluz, J. Valls, and G. Nomine, *Angew. Chem.*, 1965, 185.

65. C. S. Rao and D. K. Banerjee, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 1611.

66. A. J. Birch and H. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1882.

Birch *et al.*⁶⁷ could be methylated following the directions of Stetter and Klanke,⁶⁸ and the crude reaction product (132) directly cyclized with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid to give the tricyclic unsaturated ketone (133). Catalytic hydrogenation of (133) furnished the *trans*-benzodecalone (134) in almost quantitative yield.

The structure and configuration of the compound (134) were proved by degrading it to the known^{67,28} *trans*-1-keto-8-methyl-4,5-(4'-methoxybenzo)-hydrindane (136). To this end the compound (134) was oxidized⁶⁹ with potassium hypiodite, and the crude diacid (135) was esterified and converted to the ketone (136) following Bachmann's procedure²⁸, the identity being established by direct comparison with an authentic specimen.

In most of the syntheses of different steroids from (65, a), the first step has been to subject it to Birch reduction. We⁷⁰ also carried out the Birch reduction of the benzdecalol (137), prepared by sodium borohydride reduction of the ketone (134), to obtain the unsaturated keto alcohol (138).

67. A. J. Birch, H. Smith, and R. E. Thornton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1339.

68. H. Stetter and E. Klauke, *Ber.*, 1953, **86**, 513.

69. J. Heer, J. R. Billeter, and K. Miescher, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1945, **28**, 991.

70. D. K. Banerjee and B. Sugavanam, unpublished work.